

STUDIES ON 'LIPASE' FROM OIL SEEDS. PART IV. SYNTHESIS OF SOME ESTERS BY LIPASE

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Synthesis of some more aliphatic and aromatic esters by lipase from castor seeds has been studied in order to find out the effect of alkyl, aromatic, saturated and unsaturated groups on the synthesis of esters.

Some more esters have been synthesised using acetone-dried lipase from castor seeds in order to find out the effect of alkyl, aromatic, saturated, unsaturated groups, etc., on the enzymic synthesis of esters. So the syntheses of butyl stearate, butyl oleate, benzyl benzoate, benzyl butyrate, butyl butyrate, phenol, resorcinol and pyrogallol esters of benzoic acid, ethyl, glycol and glycerine esters of benzoic acid have been carried out and the results are recorded below.

TABLE I

Esters.	Percentage synthesis on the					
	1st day.	2nd, day.	3rd day.	4th day.	5th day.	6th day.
A. Butyl stearate	3.7	11.2	18.5	20.2	27.6	35.2
Butyl oleate	16.5	29.7	40.2	50.7	52.5	62.7
B. Phenol benzoate	2.8	4.8	5.2	11.8	15.6	14.9
Ethyl ..	1.9	4.2	4.8	8.5	12.6	12.9
Resorcinol ..	1.8	3.7	7.4	9.2	12.6	16.6
Glycol ..	1.0	2.8	5.0	9.0	11.2	16.8
Pyrogallol ..	5.4	10.2	19.5	32.8	31.6	...
Glycerine ..	4.6	7.5	18.2	28.6	30.2	29.8
C. Benzyl benzoate	6.9	14.2	22.8	25.6	28.9	27.2
Butyl butyrate	11.2	13.3	14.8	20.5	24.5	28.8
Benzyl ..	7.5	12.9	21.8	23.2	24.0	23.9
Butyl benzoate	7.6	9.6	11.2	14.8	16.9	15.8

From Table I (A) it is found that the percentage synthesis of the ester is always more in case of an unsaturated acid than a saturated one. So a clear distinction can be made between saturated and unsaturated compounds, (*i.e.*, single and double bond compound), since the percentage synthesis of the ester increases with unsaturation, which proves evidently the statement that unsaturated compounds are more reactive.

From Table I (B) it can be inferred that even though the percentage synthesis of the ester increases as the number of (OH) group increases in the alcohol in the aliphatic as well as aromatic series, still the percentage is always more in case of an aromatic compound than the aliphatic one.

From Table I (C) it is found that the percentage synthesis of the ester is always more when both the alcohol and acid used are aromatic than when both are aliphatic. Further, the percentage synthesis in case of esters where both alcohol and acid belong to the same family (*i.e.*, aliphatic or aromatic) is always more than one in which they belong to different families.